

THE ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURES AND ITS ECONOMICAL AND SOCIAL EFFICIENCY

Actuality of Organizational Structures in the Market Economy

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Abstract. Object: In the competitive world of the market economy, every economic unit tries organizing everyday activities. Creating a set of suitable and cost-efficient organizational structures and making competitive products and services, top managers should find the mechanisms of building alternative ways of organizational structures. Methods: This paper presents the traditional and modern management structures, their historical steps, and developed methods. In this footfall of the market economy, companies in developing countries should build their management system's organizational structure. They should advance a management system, managerial behaviours, and new management styles of developed ones. For this purpose in this research has learned organizational structures of developed companies. The investigation discusses the emergence, formation, and modern appearance of management structures that evaluate organizational structures' importance in enterprises and companies' activities, using vivid examples. Findings: Then, it has shown some forms of developed organizational structures of companies with the assessment of their highest role in management. In the conclusions and recommendations, we offer our approaches to solving existing organizational problems using the historical period of development to this day.

Keywords: *Organizational structure, management, structure, strategy, mission, elements, opened, closed, global, regional, local, modeling, integration, tied aspects of construction, value, personal, formation and reformation.*

We take all necessary legal measures to become one of the top 50 countries in the Doing Business ranking of the World Bank. The government should organize the effective implementation of relevant activities.

From President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's address to the Oliy Majlis

I. INTRODUCTION

The basis and content of management activities are reflected in its organizational management structure. The scope, goals, and objectives of management activities, its relationship with other management structures, integration, and appropriate selection of management elements that are parted of the structure are reflected in its daily activities.

At the time of the emergence of primitive society, the unification of the wild peoples in the struggle for survival led to the emergence of a primitive society. The formation of this society led to the transition of people to a new stage of life. Because primitive society leads to the development of typical and universal rules that should be obeyed by all people who are parted of it, it is not difficult to determine whether a particular primitive society's organizational system consists of subordinates and society. Hence, from the historicity perspective, governance structures are considered a unique form of humanity's evolutionary formation. In the future, the combination of several primitive communities led to the emergence of nations and peoples. The management of such vast countries and communities, their consolidation and protection, leads to the emergence of complex governing structures such as authority, government, state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Although the theory is a fully formed science, its first scientific concepts' authorship continues to this day. Max Weber, a well-known European German researcher, and sociologist are considered the founder of this science, whose works were published in the United States in the second half of the 1940s. Among American scholars, Henri Fayol, Chester Bernard, and other authors are traditionally regarded as leaders in organizational management structures.

The ideas of the German sociologist, lawyer, economist, and historian Max Weber (1864 –1920) were based on the expression of a bureaucratic approach in the development of management and organizational theory. In his research on the improvement of group activities, Weber pointed out that it is the most effective way of functioning for any organized group, coordinated with relevant rules. Weber sought an answer to the question of what should be done to "make the organization work like a machine." He believed that it was possible to divide the organization into components and accelerate each of them' work; proposed a precise regulation of employees' number and functions and organizations' construction on a linear basis. Weber stressed the need to manage the organization on a rational ("objective") basis. [1]

Henri Fayol (1841–1925) was a French mining engineer, head of a large mining and metallurgical company, theorist and management practitioners, and founder of Administrative Management. He is one of the classical scholars who described the organization as a theoretical science in his works.

H. Fayol developed the first complete concept of management and initially proposed concepts such as “**management functions**” and “**management principles.**” The basic ideas and methods of the school of administrative management were formed in 1920–1950. The fourteen principles of management created by the file are recommendations for creating a meaningful organizational structure.

Chester Barnard (1886–1961) is one of the most prominent system-based approach representatives, studying enterprises as a social system. For twenty years, he served as President of Bell Telephone Company in New York. He expressed his ideas in his books *The Functions of an Administrator* (1938), *Organization and Management* (1948), and others. The activities of organizations and their managers were analyzed on the basis of a system-based approach. [1]

Ch. Bernard believed that the physical and biological constraints inherent in human beings force them to unite into groups (social systems) of coordinated action and that people’s subsequent collaboration within their capacity depends on results (achievement) and efficiency (cost minimization). Such a system can be divided into two parts: organizational, which involves only the interaction of people and all other elements. “**When people come together and formally decide to unite their efforts to achieve familiar goals, they create an organization,**” - Bernard said.

The emergence of organizational theory in the 1940s-1950s brought together R. Merton (Columbia University) and G.Simon. It also has the idea that it is related to Simon’s activities. In 1956, a group of psychologists, economists, and political scientists under his leadership (now Carnegie Mellon University) published the first issue of the "Quarter of Administrative Sciences" at the Carnegie University of Technology.

Simon Herbert Alexander (1916–2001) was an American scientist who studied the principles and processes of decision-making in human activity fields, achieved immediate results in many sciences and humanities, mathematics and economics, and was awarded the 1978 Nobel Prize. [1]

In 1947, Simon published his first book on classical administrative behavior. In addition to studying the principles of organization, he set the boundaries of the concept of "limited rationality". He won the Nobel Prize thirty years later.

The author of the works of the famous Austrian-American scientist Karl Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1901–1972), the theory of general systems, and the theory of open systems greatly contributed to the development of the organization.

Some modern researchers argue that organizational theory did not exist as a separate scientific theory until the late 1960s. All well-known research in the field of organizations belonged to schools of organizational sociology of scientific management. By the late 1960s and early 1970s, management gradually replaced the social aspect of organizational theory, and the discipline itself began to be taught in business schools focused on training professional managers. Since then, organizational theory has come to be seen as a discipline that allows organizations to understand, predict, and manage their behavior. Today, we can rightly say that the Russian scientist, the famous thinker-encyclopedic of the twentieth century Alexander Alexandrovich Bogdanov, laid the foundations of modern ideas about organization theory. Alexander Alexandrovich Bogdanov (Malinovsky) (1873–1928) - one of the famous Russian scientists, economists, philosophers, doctors, science fiction writers, founders, and heads of the world's first blood transfusion institute.

A.Bogdanov's ideas on organizational structures are described in such works as "Essays on General Organizational Science" (1921), "Organizational Science and Economic Planning" (1921), "Economic Technologies and Organizational Foundations of Economics" (1923). The main work of the scientist is "Tectology," which is a fundamental monograph. It was written in 1910 and is called "General Organizational Science." This work’s starting point teaches the need to approach any event from its organization’s perspective.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A management structure based on a system-based approach allows the organization to be considered a system consisting of several interrelated elements. Initially, the theory of organizational management structures was applied in the exact sciences and technology. It has been used in management sciences since the late 1950s, which can be considered a unique management science school achievement. As the founder of the new direction, Ludwig von Bertalanffy is worth mentioning as a scientist. The system-based approach’s main content is based on purpose, reflecting the organization’s most important feature, through which this system differs from others.

No system-based approach is a set of principles for managers but a way of systematizing organizations and management. A system is a type of integrity that consists of contributing to the properties of any integrity (systems managed by all organizations) composed of interconnected separate parts (elements).

Modeling of organizational systems:

Closed systems - have strictly defined boundaries; the method of its actions does not depend on the external environment’s factors. **Opened systems** are a form of organizational structure characterized by their interaction with the surrounding (external) environment and can adapt (adapt).

Figure 1. Stapes of formation of the organizational structure of companies and institutions¹

The organization and institutions require a unique management structure to achieve its effective and uninterrupted operation. The organizational management structure’s effectiveness is a relative indicator, which is assessed depending on the system’s capabilities, the degree of realization of the system capabilities, and ultimately, the factors of satisfaction of specific needs. We can summarize it using the following formula:

$$E = f(P_a - P_y) \rightarrow \max_n Y_n, \text{ there} \quad [1]$$

P_a - The capacity of the system;

P_y - The degree to which the system uses its capabilities

Y_n - Satisfaction of needs

The main task of the company's Management is to maximize the (Y_n). Gaining for (Y_n), it is necessary to create an integrated, optimally linked chain of its organizational structure to give it a reliable assessment. Because any company or institution is an integrated open system, it directly impacts its life cycle, requiring that they be organized in a continuous connection with external environmental factors. Here, the goals and objectives, strategy, and mission of forming the organizational management structure should be defined as the most pressing management issue. These factors play an essential role in expressing the life cycle as the first and most relevant and decisive link. It is inconceivable that any organization, whose goals and objectives, strategy, and mission are unknown, will start operating and be managed.

It is appropriate that the requirements and conditions for the formation of the goals and objectives of the organization should be as follows:

- ✓ The set goals and objectives should be achievable and should not interfere with the coherence of the elements of the system;
- ✓ It should be time-limited; that is, it should represent the work to be done at a particular time interval;
- ✓ Goals and objectives should explain by the socio-economic status of the enterprise, the availability of financial resources;
- ✓ It should be concise and concise, understandable and clear to be implemented;

Figure 2. The order of the growth of the duration of the formation of organizational goals²

- ✓ The strategy and mission of the enterprise should not contradict;
- ✓ Goals and objectives should not refuse laws, government decrees, and orders.

¹ Source: Created by the author

² Source: Created by the author

Once the goal is identified, its long-term viability process is assessed. The strategies and missions of enterprises and institutions for the next few years are identified.

Once the goals and objectives are clear, its current state's performance indicator is analyzed in depth. The prime purpose of the analysis is to devise a strategy for the future development of the enterprise. Because the current goals and objectives require the implementation of strategic plans for the next few years, in line with the directions and accordance. Strategies are also adopted for the short, medium, and long term. It depends on the type of activity of the enterprise or institution, its customers' size, and the state of the competitive environment.

Figure 3. The process of mission and strategy formation concerning goals and objectives³

Once the goals and objectives, their main direction, and final strategies have been developed, the next step is to assess its level of value and its internal and external environment. A strategy's value primarily determines by customers and employees of the enterprise's value. Suppose the system has value for both situations. In that case, a mission will be developed in the future to ensure that this strategy is implemented perfectly and sustainably.

The main difference between a mission and a strategy is that it embodies the psychology of the organization.

The following are examples of the missions of world-renowned companies:

FACEBOOK MISSION:

"It is about empowering people to connect more openly and faster with the world."

ALIBABA GROUP MISSION:

"Make it easier to do business anywhere."

BBC MISSION:

"Enrich people's lives with informative, educational, and entertaining programs and services."

MICROSOFT MISSION:

"To allow people and business people worldwide to realize their full potential."

WALMART MISSION:

"We save people money so they can live better."

LOREAL MISSION:

"Offering the best cosmetic breakthroughs in terms of quality, effectiveness, and safety for all women and men worldwide."

UNITED NATIONS MISSION:

"Ensuring international peace and security."

³ Source: Created by the author

It is impossible to imagine the formation of an organizational mission without top managers, CEOs, and their leaders. Because the mission is the central part of all organizing activities. It integrates all the enterprise or organization's goals and objectives, strategic plans, tactical actions and is understandable and quickly understandable. The most significant part is that the enterprise's values can be assessed as the principal, highest element of the organizational management structure, understanding its relationship with the internal and external environment. In the following tables, some of the world scientists have developed coefficients and intervals for evaluating the effectiveness of organizational structures in quantitative and qualitative terms.

The name of the coefficient	Formulation	Parameters of coefficients	Value
The degree of accuracy of the target	$K_1 = m_1/m_0$	m_1 - the number of units whose goals are defined and interrelated m_0 - the total number of units	1
The level of coverage of the target	$K_2 = T_n/T_{ch}$	T_n - the number of normative goals of the department T_{ch} - the number of purposes of the division reflected in the charter rules	1
Level of coverage of functions	$K_3 = F_{an}/F_{dn}$	F_a - the actual number of functions performed in the organizational structure F_n - the default number of tasks	1
Coefficient of repetition and independence of functions	$K_4 = (F_{da} - F_n)/F_n$	F_{di} - the amount of duplication and unrelated tasks in the system	1
The coefficient of specialization of the j-function	$K_5 = m_0/(m_0 + \sum mt_j)$	m_{aj} - the number of sections that repeat the j-normative functions	1
j-target specialization coefficient	$K_6 = m_0/(m_0 + \sum mt_j)$	m_{gj-j} - number of repeating units of the target	1
The proportion of employees whose rights and responsibilities are defined	$K_7 = E_{nem}/E$	E_{nem} - the number of employees whose rights and responsibilities are defined D is the total number of employees	1
An average assessment of the degree to which the rights of subordinate employees to perform their duties are secured	$K_8 = 1/((\sum(an+ap)/2)/n)$	an and ap j-Assess whether the rights of the team member and his supervisor are secured	0.33

Table 1. Systematic indicators of assessing the effectiveness of the organizational structure⁴

It can be seen from the data in this table that the evaluation of the effectiveness of organizational structures is based on the assessment of the goals and objectives assigned to functional units about the system purpose, legal security, and level of specialization of functions, accuracy, and transparency.

Koef-t	Value	Recommended Value	Rejection rate	Quality assessment	Score
K_1	0.80	1.00	0.20	Satisfactory	8
K_2	1.10	1.00	0.10	Fits	7
K_3	0.64	1.00	0.36	Low-level compatibility	9
K_4	0.70	1.00	0.30	Satisfactory	5
K_5	0.35	1.00	0.65	Low-level compatibility	6
K_6	0.22	1.00	0.78	Unsatisfactory	8
K_7	1.00	1.00	0.00	Fits	4
K_8	0.40	0.33	0.07	Fits	6

Table 2. Organizational structure efficiency matrix

⁴ Fedorova N.N. *Organizatsionnaya struktura upravleniya predpriyatiem: Ucheb. Posobie.* - M.: TK Velbi, 2003. - 256 c.

The quality of the organizational management structure is also assessed. The target structure of the organizational structure is evaluated based on appropriate intervals.

The limit of rejection in the integral assessment of the target structure of the system	0–0.15	0.15–0.35	0.35–0.65	> 0.65
Evaluate the quality of the organizational structure	Fits	Satisfactory	Satisfactory at the lower level	Incompatible

Table 3. Qualitative Assessment Intervals of Organizational Structures⁵

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The introduction of all types of business entities, enterprises, and institutions operating in Uzbekistan into the diversified enterprises’ organizational structures will lead to higher economic and social activities.

Organizational structures are divided into linear, linear-functional, functional, matrix organizational structures, depending on the process’s scale.

Organizational management structures can also be divided into national and international, regional, international-regional, inter-regional organizational structures. The above formation conditions and principles are fully applicable even when working with these structures.

The foremost is that the description of organizational structures corresponds to the organization’s goals and objectives, serves to implement long-term strategic plans and does not cause complications in its life cycle. Also, there should be no redundant elements in the management structure of the organization.

In the following examples, we give an individual assessment of its organizational management structures using an organization specializing in products’ production.

For export-only activities, the Export Department requires the following organizational elements to be considered.

Figure 4. Elementary Organizational Structure of Export Department⁶

This structure is a view of a linear-functional management structure. Because this type of organizational structure can be seen in both functional and linear control elements. A characteristic feature of the linear structure is that all functional departments receive assignments from a single manager directly one step above. That is, the self-management of each applicable department does not apply. Nevertheless, the tasks that need to be done are performed independently by each available unit. Such structures can be observed mainly in enterprises and organization’s management structures, exporters, and importers, specializing in providing small types of products and services. This type of enterprise allows you to control the products and services produced. Hence, the figure above’s management structure is more specific to enterprises and organizations with less functional responsibilities.

However, enterprises and organizations, international holdings, international associations, and cartels where the production scales are branched and expanded, and their organizational structure will look complicated.

⁵ Vissema X. *Menedjment v podrazdeleniyax firms: Eng. - M.: Infra - M, 1996.*

⁶ Source: Created and developed by the author

Figure 5. The systematical division of organizational structure of an international company⁷

Nevertheless, it will be organized based on management elements inherent in traditional organizational structures because it is impossible to create multi-branch management structures without the usual control elements. As proof, the international companies' organizational structures shown in Figure 2 are characterized by the executive, traditional functional units, departments serving to cultivate multi-sectoral products, international regions, and subsidiaries' distribution in them. The management of such international organizations is the classification of the units' geographical location in the regions, the types of products and services grown in them, and the general administrative management procedure with subsidiaries' help. The role and place of subsidiaries in the direct impact on the development of this organization are invaluable.

As prominent representatives of the international organization in the regions, perform all the main structure' tasks and responsibilities, make decisions based on joint missions and strategies, develop goals. They work extensively with clients. Companies can also be formed as diversified units based on customers' needs and requirements in the subsidiaries' regions. Alternatively, in adopting one-year plans, of course, based on the regions' geographical location, considering customers' needs and desires. While the organizational structures of subsidiaries are similar, their chief goals and objectives will be different. The strategic plans, mission, form and level of international competition developed by the global regions' business entity.

To avoid complicating international organizations' management, each traditional organizational management can also be described as a distribution of structure-based components in international regions. It is reflected in the system-based approach to the management of complex managed international organizational structures. For instance, in the study and management of the state of trade in the territories in the global system, in the development of strategic plans, strategic goals for each, in-depth analysis of the economic and financial situation in the regions, in further improving the marketing capacity of the areas; more applicable in detection. Also, the organizational management structures of multidisciplinary, international companies such as Coca-Cola, Nike, and Oriflame can be studied as a basis.

Example 1. Oriflame was founded in 1967 by two brothers and a friend and is now an international direct-selling cosmetics company with operations in more than 60 countries. The company offers various Swedish natural cosmetics produced using the most modern technologies. About 3 million consultants work with Oriflame, and the company's annual turnover is about 1.4 billion euros.

⁷ Source: Created and developed by the author

Figure 6. Oriflame's international organizational and managerial structure⁸

Oriflame offers a business for the people worldwide who want to start making money and pursue their dreams and plans, an excellent opportunity to start their own business. The company’s unique business concept is **“Earn today and make your dreams come true tomorrow.”** The fundamental principle of our work is respect for people and nature, which is enshrined in the social and environmental policy of Oriflame. The company is also a co-founder of the World Children's Fund and is proud to be involved in numerous charitable projects worldwide. These results are based on the effective international organizational structures of the activities of the company. By their effective administrative system, they give the highest marks: around 1.4 billion euros annual turnover, about 3 million Oriflame consultants, representatives in more than 60 countries, about 7,500 Oriflame employees, several products with about 1000 brands of natural Swedish innovative cosmetics and catalogs.

Figure 7. The inter-regional organizational structure of the foreign company⁹

40 languages. We can review how works organizational structure of Oriflame by Figures (7,8,9,10) below. The focus in international organizations’ inter-regional governance structure is to facilitate an in-depth analysis of factors such as regions, geographical location, specific characteristics, mentality, and clients’ income in these regions.

The international inter-regional organizational structure shown in Figure 5 above focuses on local offices, branches, and networks of enterprises and organizations operating in the Americas, Europe, and Asia to show you what I mean. It specializes in regulating the existing management process in the departments of Management in these three regions. It is characterized by analyzing specific aspects of sales, finance, marketing, and human resources for the Americas, Europe, and Asia, based on which management decisions are made, to find optimal solutions to problems.

Another example is the management structure in Figure 5 in the analysis and organization of international or inter-regional management of products and services. Because there is a need for such an organizational structure for the global Management of the production, goodwill, trade, marketing, or economic and financial performance of types A, B, C in America, Europe, and Asia. The organizational management structure is essential in successfully managing multidisciplinary, international enterprises and organizations to construct its unique management structure. Here, the perfect depiction of each type of product in selected regions of all elements, from sales to work with employees, directly impacts organizing such complex structures at the international level. The composition of the corporate product should be at the heart of a complex management structure.

⁸ Source: Created and developed by the author

⁹ Source: Created and developed by the author

Figure 8. The organizational structure of the global production process¹⁰

Figure 9. The organizational structure of global matrix management¹¹

An example of a more efficient global management of international products and services is the matrix management structure of the products shown in Figure 6 below. This structure is a more complex management structure, which will be necessary to realize the distribution and management of hundreds of products in many international regions. It also allows for an optimized distribution of costs for all manufactured products and services through a matrix management structure. Imagine, by evaluating, the efficiency of the production of types A, B, and C products in the American region, it becomes possible to conduct a comparative analysis of them.

¹⁰ Source: Created and developed by the author

¹¹ Source: Created and developed by the author

Determining the intensity of the same product's production in different regions allows for severe competition and control, even within branches within the same organization but operating in different regions. Here, forming personnel in the regions also leads to implementation of the global distribution and redistribution of personnel based on the procedures in force in the regions and serves the company's strategic goals.

Another distinct feature of the matrix management structure is its broad application of global corporate governance principles and corporate governance tools, distinguished from other management structures. That is, the use of the most actively used forms of Management allows for implementation.

Figure 10. Evolution of the organizational structure of globalized companies¹²

The diagram shown in Figure 7 can also be used in multidisciplinary enterprises and organizations by introducing those, as mentioned above, international organizational structures of management in individual cases or by combining the features of all of them. Multi-sectoral conglomerates, concerns, and multinational companies develop organizational management structures and strategies for different areas. Senior representatives of the top management team, forming a complex management chain, do it by themselves. Such international organizations are developed because of coordinated, situational governance principles of global governance. These forms of globalized control are based on strategies with directions and implementing a global strategy in a coordinated way. Here, it is also possible to organize management by polarization following international organizations' product geography, partners and competitors. Because the factors that pose the most significant risk to international organizations can hurt the entire management system and ultimately lead to many financial losses in the short term. Therefore, a central emphasis is placed on the management structure designed to organize global matrix production. Through a worldwide matrix management structure, the management process of conglomerates can be maximized. Rapid decision-making is not unique to such facilities. Leaders of such systems try organizing management mainly by developing long-term decisions, goals, and strategies. Economic and financial analysis of the production or provision of services is also conducted regularly because of agreements with organizations with a high level of audit certification and license at the international level. The results can be presented to the organization's top managers and international stakeholders because changes in such giant and globalized companies' financial performance can affect the competitive environment and the entire economic system, some international indices.

PROBLEMS AND DISCUSSION

While learning how effectively organizes organizational structures, we find some problems that top managers should know. The difficulties of organizational structures could divide into some types for learning and assessing them accurately. They are problems of

a) The formation of mission and strategies of the companies and organizations.

While top managers begin the formation of mission and strategies, they have made decisions like as grabbing all sectors of the market, revolutionary way of production planning, realizing decisions in a short time, not concerning strategies of all competitive partners, boring ways to solve a problem, do not know the values of mission and strategy for the clients and employment each other, and i.e.

b) Restructure of management vision and functions

When top managers review the company's organizational structures, they can make restructuring management professional errors. Mistakes of unsupported elements of the organization, fundamental mistakes and illogical steps of the growth planning, not knowing of how effectively divide the visions, goals and functions correctly, the problems of optimization of business process and i.e.

¹² Source: Created and developed by the author

c) Finding behavioral manners of personals of organizations

Behavioral Management is an effective way of managing and working with personals in the most advanced companies and organizations. They influence the business process using human behavioral qualities. Top managers work their best with personals and solve many human behavior problems, their communication etiquette.

d) Optimization of elements of organizational structures

Optimization of organizational structures plays the highest role in forming and reforming the systems. By making optimization, Top managers can staff cuts in any direction of the design. For now, there are not any practical ways of optimization of organizational structures for every company. However, we can find some subjective approach to solve it. For instance, there are so many problems between integrating companies' activities in developing countries with developed ones.

e) Integration with international organizational structures

Integration of organizational structures is the main problem of products and services of export-import companies, international conglomerates, and some international organizations. The leading causes are legal inconsistency, behavioral differences, personals, and differences in the population's living conditions and income degrees. I think these are the most objective factors for integration with international organizations.

f) Finding legalization formations of managerial structures

Top managers' most necessary vision for the formation or reformations of organizational structures is choosing the most legal forms of organizational structures. Any illegal form of structure can destroy all administrative systems. Therefore, while working with formation and reformation, top managers should attract qualified lawyers.

g) Rejection of illegal types of departments and units**h) Liberalization between the elements of organizational structures****CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS**

The essence of organizational management structures' content, their role in management activities, and enterprises and organizations' role in improving daily activities' efficiency is enormous. Because the management systems, its elements together represent all the organization's specific organs, are the basis of the factors that highly affect its continuity and coexistence with the external environment.

Based on the results obtained from the examples analyzed above, it is proposed to generalize Management's organizational structures into three main links, i.e., higher-level governing bodies. These include the Board of Directors, the President and the Executive Director, and the Administration.

Such a senior management structure is mainly typical of multidisciplinary, large-scale production or service companies, multinational companies, concerns, conglomerates, etc. Depending on the type of activity's size or scope, the number of these joints will decrease.

The board of directors or shareholders is reflected in the company's charter in implementing corporate governance management with shareholders' participation. Suppose the company has organized its activities in several countries worldwide. In that case, President and CEOs conduct the post-shareholder Management in such enterprises. While the board of directors or shareholders is directly involved in developing the company's main directions, goals, strategies, and mission, the President and the Executive Director directly impact the legal formation, planning, implementation, and coordination of their decisions and tasks, and responsibilities. Subsequent managers are of administrative importance; they directly from the staff develop personnel policy, address the company's economic and financial problems and establish external relations, considering the company's internal and external environmental factors and advanced means of communication. Are representatives of the management unit, which is directly responsible for the implementation in the formation of computer and electronic control systems? It should not be allowed to become more complicated in the shape of management structures. The simpler the management structure, the more influential the management can be.

Figure 11. The traditional scheme of the organizational structure of multinational companies¹³

Based on the general concepts and conclusions developed above in the formation of the organizational structures, the relevant findings and recommendations for the economy of Uzbekistan are

- ✓ In the more profound application of the principles of a market economy, it is suitable for business entities and entrepreneurs to use functional organizational structures in the formation of organizational structures of their activities;
- ✓ It is necessary to functionalize the rules of administrative discipline further and liberalize directive regulation;
- ✓ A deep understanding of the fact that linear management structures do not fully comply with the rules of a market economy, pay great attention to the formation of systems that can operate independently instead of the principle of leadership in organizational structures;
- ✓ Frequent monitoring of foreign experience, the formation of a leadership structure in the management structures of enterprises and organizations that can make tactical decisions aimed at developing strategy and mission, monitoring its regular implementation, ensuring healthy competition with competitors;
- ✓ Transfer of enforcement mechanisms in enterprises and organizations to more simplified and democratized systems;
- ✓ Achieve the formation of the organizational structure because of a perfect division of labor; avoid duplication within its constituent elements, the appearance of personnel in the division of delivery according to the number, scope, relevance;
- ✓ Formation based on the fact that there are no conflicts between the links of the organizational structure;
- ✓ In the formation of the organizational structure, the main emphasis should be on creating a management system that can provide quality feedback between departments and managers, from ordinary staff;
- ✓ One of the main requirements of today is to form the elements of the organizational structure in such a way that it does not interfere with easy integration with other systems, to meet the tactical and strategic decisions of competing organizations and enterprises;
- ✓ It is necessary to express all the system's essential elements, not duplicate each other, and be easily linked.

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¹³ Source: Created and developed by the author

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